

Open Science in Theory and Practice

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The idea of “open science” has become a central reference for science policy both globally and specifically in the European Union. It’s hard to object to something being open when the alternative is for it to be in some sense “closed”, especially when that alternative remains largely implicit. And yet, practical enthusiasm for open science doesn’t always match its aspirational attractiveness, and scepticism is by no means limited to those with a vested economic interest in specific forms of closure, e.g. with respect to publications.

This suggests that open science practices, and the institutional frameworks within which they are set, deserve more detailed attention than they sometimes receive. This was the point of the recently completed Horizon Europe OPUS project (<https://opusproject.eu/>), which looked in detail at some of the issues in embedding open science within routine practices. A major focus of the project was on researcher assessment: if people are supposed to be engaging in open science, then how does their engagement (or lack of it) affect how they are assessed by the various institutions they relate to? In addition, a specific strand of work within OPUS was devoted to trust issues in open science, and specifically to trust barriers to open science engagement. This is the strand I was responsible for, working with Pierre Winicki, who’s my business partner in PHGD Group affiliate TrustInside.

So, what is the “closed science” that needs to be opened up? In fairly general terms, this is quite easy to state. Science is “closed”:

- a. when it’s separate from political, social and cultural dynamics, i.e. operates according to

its own internal logic—science defined, run and assessed by scientists;

- b. when within scientific communities it is closed by institutional barriers and habits of gatekeeping, broadly understood, incorporating preconditions for access to agenda-setting, to data, to publications, etc.

It will be noted that these characteristics aren’t obviously “bad”. In fact, they have been central to the definition and institutional organisation of science as a distinctive realm of social activity – to what makes science science.ⁱ Nonetheless, the view that opening up closed science is desirable builds on three considerations:

- a. closed science entrenches inequalities in both access and benefit sharing, contrary to the aspiration expressed in article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights;
- b. closed science hinders desirable epistemic transformations, e.g. towards transdisciplinarity;
- c. closed science limits social responsiveness and responsibility, an issue given particular prominence by scandals or controversies in the 1980s and 90s stemming from the closure of technoscience (nuclear risk, HIV contamination in blood transfusion systems, bovine spongiform encephalopathy, genetically modified organisms, etc.). In a word, closed science creates specific trust issues.

This normative lineage is clearly visible in the definitions adopted in international instruments promoting open science. Thus, UNESCO’s 2021 Recommendation on Open Science states:

Open science is about making sure not only that scientific knowledge is accessible but also that the production of that knowledge itself is inclusive, equitable and sustainable. (...) Open science has the potential of making the scientific process more transparent, inclusive and democratic.

Other versions of open science differ as to details, but the general thrust is the same.

Which leads to the question: do open science practices, in real-world conditions, produce the benefits to be expected from more open science? If not, what are the barriers, the unforeseen side effects, the structural biases? For the purposes of this brief overview, four specific questions deserve mention.

1. Does opening science increase trust?

The answer seems to be: not necessarily. Contemporary patterns of politicisation of science—of which climate science, virology, and many aspects of environmental science are exemplary—appear, in a specific political climate, to feed on openness. Perhaps this can be understood in terms of Bismarck's metaphor of the sausage factory: the more one knows about the processes by which science is produced, the less one can trust the product. At the very least, opening up scientific processes to lay examination depends on significant public understanding of why science is done the way it is.

The work done in OPUS also points to an additional issue. There are trust issues within science communities, exemplified by issues relating to data sharing as well as to concerns about misalignment between the various kinds of incentives embedded in assessment and evaluation.

¹ A central topic in 20th century sociology of science, e.g. Pierre Bourdieu, *Science de la science et réflexivité* (Paris: Raisons d'agir, 2001), borrowing explicitly from Robert K. Merton, *The*

2. Does opening science increase social responsiveness and responsibility?

It's a fairly new agenda, so the evidence is inconclusive. But while increased stakeholder involvement in science probably does promote greater responsiveness to social demands, those demands may be highly biased in terms of an equitable assessment of social needs, which is what the human rights principle of benefit sharing logically demands. The connection between responsiveness and responsibility depends on a public culture of science that is compatible with openness, but not logically entailed by it.

3. Does open science limit political or corporate interference?

Hard to say on current evidence. Openness of protocols, data, review processes, etc., can, at least in highly politicised areas of science, have the effect of—or be weaponised towards—undermining scientific authority in its traditional forms, without replacing it by any functional alternative.

4. Does open science reduce scientific inequalities?

It's clearly too early to say. But there is a legitimate concern that more open science will tend to restrict participation in the scientific process while broadening the distribution of its benefits—by analogy with the way in which open access publishing, seen from developing countries, can make it easier to read and harder to publish.

In other words, no doubt unsurprisingly, there are still big gaps between the principles of open science and the practical mechanisms designed to achieve it.

Sociology of Science: Theoretical and Empirical Investigations (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1973).